

Green valorization of olive-tree waste biomass

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Abstract

Olive trees are regularly pruned. The branches removed are usually burnt on-site creating a significant atmospheric pollution at the expense of precious energy resources. Recently adopted alternative options involve mechanical shedding of the branches. The shredded branches are either dried pelleted and used as solid fuel for energy, or composted and used as fertilizers, or left on the olive groves to decay naturally. In general they are treated on-site because their transportation is considered problematic due to their size and they relatively insignificant market value. However, this oil rich biomass, which has always been considered as a problem is actually a resource of important added value, since products and methods to recover them in a viable form do exist. Their application has never been considered due to the inconvenience imposed by the difficulty in moving the generated waste-biomass due to their size and the volume.

In a recent work we considered the valorization of olive-tree waste-biomass and performed an analysis of supply chains based on its thermocatalytic reforming. The supply chain considered involved the following main steps: collection and chipping of olive trees trimmings, transportation of the biomass to the conversion site, biomass conversion to syn-gas bio-oil and bio-char, product transportation, and final use. In the present study an alternative supply chain is considered; it involves the following steps: collection of olive trees trimmings and transportation to short-distances conversion sites; production of valuable pharmaceuticals employing the appropriate parts of the branches and utilizing energy provided by the further treatment of less valuable parts of the branches; left-over biomass conversion to syn-gas bio-oil and bio-char, products transportation, and final use. The environmental and economic performance of waste biomass valorization is analyzed in both cases and issues related to fluctuations of the supply chain and methods of their elimination are proposed.

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